

EXHIBIT B

Holographic Encodon Framework • Phonic-Photic Circuit • Chirality as the Ground of Valence

Direct comparison of emails where author expressly attributed research framework to Ms. Lin, to published research using the same terms and concepts in a near identical conceptual framework.

Mary Lin & Ben Sargent — Philosophy Farm Press — Lebanon, Maine
 Companion to Prior Art: Documentary Record of Origination — DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19375905

Green text marks verbatim or near-verbatim matching words and phrases between Lin's prior communications and the published papers.

The Three Published Papers

- Paper 1: Cavaglià & Tuszynski — "A physical model of neuronal membrane excitations as a mechanism of holographic image formation in brain" — Journal of Multiscale Neuroscience, 4(3):187–195, 2025
- Paper 2: Cavaglià & Tuszynski — "A unified holographic framework for neural computation and consciousness: From lipid membranes to the Schumann resonance" — BioSystems, 259:105669, 2025
- Paper 3: Firaux, Tuszynski & Cavaglià — "EMI Model: A scale-free biophysical framework for human consciousness, cognition and behaviour" — BioSystems, 259:105674, 2025

TABLE 1 — From Mary Lin to Marco Cavaglià

Emails sent directly to Cavaglià before any paper was submitted

From Mary Lin — email to Marco Cavaglià	Published paper — matching text
January 20, 2025 — subject: "fungus frastornato"	
"I cannot shake the image of membrane lamelli as holographic photographs , traded in vesicles and microplasts, with transmission of them like fiberoptic cables, holons of electrons and protons and photons in and around microtubules."	Paper 1, Abstract: " membrane as holographic plate " (Postulate 1) Paper 2, Abstract: " membrane as holographic plate " (Postulate 1)
January 20, 2025 — subject: "fungus frastornato"	
"electric and electromagnetic signals to read and record and send these 3-or-more-dimensional encodons "	Paper 1, Abstract: "holographic read-write " (Postulate 3) Paper 2, Abstract: "holographic read-write " (Postulate 3) Paper 3, Preprint: "the system can record and retrieve mental states"

January 20, 2025 — subject: "fungus frastornato"	
"the glyco-structures in extracellular space holding and shaping chiral LC/ligand water into 3-D aspects of recorded experience, with an added layer a quorum function of water and protein chirality engaged to color for emotion and valence."	Paper 2, Abstract, Postulate 2: "vicinal water as coherence medium" Paper 3, Preprint: "coherent water domains enables an informational write and read cycle... chiral water cited as substrate throughout
January 13, 2025 — subject: "Chiral spiral light"	
"How are cells creating and transducing polarized light for signalling, sensing, and memory creation and access ?" Circularly polarized biophoton emission in living organisms cited.	Paper 1 and Paper 2 throughout: polarized electromagnetic fields as encoding mechanism; memory formation via holographic interference

TABLE 2 — From Marco Cavaglià to Mary Lin

Cavaglià's own letters attributing the framework to Lin — before any paper was submitted

From Marco Cavaglià — email to Mary Lin	Published paper — matching text
January 29, 2025 — reply to "fungus frastornato" thread	
"I keep thinking about your vision of membranes as holographic encodons , the quorum sensing of language , and the structured water shaping experience — it's all been echoing in my mind." <i>Cavaglià explicitly attributes all three concepts to Lin. No co-authorship invitation was extended before publication.</i>	" membranes as holographic encodons " → Paper 1 and Paper 2: "membrane as holographic plate" (Postulate 1) " quorum sensing of language " → Paper 3 (EMI model): founding concept of scale-free architecture, introduced without attribution " structured water shaping experience " → Paper 2 and Paper 3: "vicinal water as coherence medium"; "coherent water domains enables write and read cycle"
January 29, 2025 — same email	
"I'd love to explore how we can bring some of these ideas into a shared project."	Note: No co-authorship invitation was subsequently extended before any of the three papers was submitted or published. These ideas — attributed to Lin by

	Cavaglià in this letter — appear as the foundational claims of all three papers.
January 31, 2025 — follow-up (addressed "Dear Maria Caterina")	
"I sincerely apologize for missing both of our planned meetings...I would love to reconnect and continue our discussion...bring these ideas into a shared project."	Note: This letter confirms a pattern of engagement with Lin's framework and repeated intention to collaborate — followed by publication without attribution or co-authorship invitation.

TABLE 3 — From Mary Lin to ABI Officers

Email sent to C.S. Munford (President, ABI) and Richard Watson (Chief Scientific Officer, ABI), December 18, 2024 — Marco Cavaglià is a named researcher in the ABI research proposal

From Mary Lin — email to ABI officers, December 18, 2024	Published paper — matching text
December 18, 2024 — subject: "Compiling our thoughts in a paper" — sent to Steven Lehar, C.S. Munford, Richard Watson	
<p>Explicit statement of phonon-to-photon transduction framework, Schumann resonance coupling, and piezoelectric properties of cellular structures as a unified biological signaling architecture. Lightning cited as analogous piezoelectric phenomenon. Morphological standing wave patterns proposed as research direction.</p> <p><i>Note: C.S. Munford is President of the Agential Biology Institute (ABI). Richard Watson is Chief Scientific Officer of ABI. Marco Cavaglià is a named researcher in the ABI research proposal (agentialbiology.org/research-proposal). All three are ABI colleagues.</i></p>	<p>Paper 2 title: "From lipid membranes to the Schumann resonance"</p> <p>Paper 2 Abstract: "synchronize with the Schumann resonance — the Earth's natural electromagnetic background — via cross-scale resonance"</p> <p>Paper 3 Abstract: "consciousness is the result of a coherent resonance between the brain's electromagnetic fields and the Earth's field" — the scale-spanning piezoelectric architecture of Lin's December 18 email stated as the paradigm shift of Paper 3</p>

SUMMARY

On January 29, 2025, Marco Cavaglià wrote to Mary Lin: *"I keep thinking about your vision of membranes as holographic encodons, the quorum sensing of language, and the structured water shaping experience — it's all been echoing in my mind."*

These three phrases are the load-bearing concepts of all three published papers. Cavaglià attributed them to Lin in writing before any paper was submitted. The papers were published without attribution to Lin.

All prior communications cited above predate the submission of any of the three papers.